

MINERALOGRAPHIC STUDY OF CHIGARGUNTA GOLD MINES, ANDHRA PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

The Chigargunta gold mine area is situated in the southern extension of the Kolar gold fields. The area is very close to the trijunction of the state boundaries of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Tamilnadu. Representative ore minerals from chigargunta Gold Mines were examined and the observations are illustrated.

Key words: Arsenopyrite, Pyrite, Galena, Paragenesis, Martization

Introduction:

The Chigargunta gold mine area is situated in the southern extension of the Kolar gold fields. The area is very close to the trijunction of the state boundaries of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Tamilnadu. Majority of the ore minerals including gold in an auriferous specimen are opaque, hence mineralographic study is made, following the procedures of Cameron (1961) and Schouten (1962). The description of the ore minerals as follows:

Literature Review:

The following Is the literature survey for study of ore minerals and to understand the paragenesis.

Cameron Eugone. N: (1961), Gilbert. G(1924), Lincoln. F.C. (1911). SaFonov. Yu. G., et all (1980), Schouten C. (1962).

Objectives :

To study the ore Minerals and to understand the paragenetic sequence.

Methodology:

Mineralographic study is the made on the representative ore minerals following the methodology of Cameron Eugone. N: (1961),

Findings:

Description of Ore Minerals:

Gold: Gold occurs in native form and shows very characteristic golden yellow colour. It is opaque and isotropic. In some cases shows weak anisotropism due to large impurities. The grain size is varying significantly. Some minutest fragments of gold are observed (Figs. 17 and 18). Gold is easily identified by virtue of its colour, but some other sulphides have also more or less similar gold colour and to distinguish them from gold, the specimen is rotated and the appearance of the fleck of doubtful mineral is observed in different lights, gold does not change in its appearance, while the rest change great or less (Lincoln, 1911). Generally, the chalcopyrite grains are mistaken for gold. In such cases the surface of the ore mounts rubbed with a drop of mercury on a chamois

pad, and examined under microscope, their colour is found to have been changed from yellow to brilliant white, while the chalcopyrite does not change (Lincoln, 1911).

Gold is generally present in fractured and brecciated arsenopyrite on quartz, which may be the only ideal condition for localization and mineralization. Specks of gold are seen in between arsenopyrite grains which are probably of angular nature. These may be due to filling up of gold along crystal boundaries and interspaces of crystals, through the flow filling and replacement processes (Figs. 13, 14 and 15). At times it is observed that the amphibolites is formed with vesicles and the voids are filled up by gold as a filled up material (Figs. 10 and 16). The overall mineralographic studies reveals Gold – Quartz – Arsenopyrite and Gold – Quartz – Pyrrhotite associations are common. Gold – pyrite association is very rare. The similar conclusion is also drawn by Safonov et al (1980).

Arsenopyrite: It is the dominant among the ore minerals. Subhedral grains of arsenopyrite with inclusions like magnetite is very common (Fig. 9). Occasionally it shows poikilitic texture in pyrrhotite. Cluster of arsenopyrite grains and exceptionally some big crystals have been exhibiting deformational features are observed (Figs. 6 and 7). At times broken and undisturbed arsenopyrite grains are also noticed (Fig. 5). Both the above findings confirm the prevalence of stress in the area, on geological past.

Pyrrhotite: Pyrrhotite is somewhat abundant ore mineral next to arsenopyrite, and is unevenly disturbed. It always occurs as massive and anhedral (Fig. 8) along with arsenopyrite and pyrite. In some cases elongation and bending nature due to the effect of stress is observed (Fig. 4). Occasionally vesicles are observed filled by some detrital material. Some cases poikilitic texture is observed (Fig. 2).

Pyrite: It is rarely observed. Euhedral grains of pyrite which are completely isotropic are noticed. (Fig. 1). Inclusions of arsenopyrite and pyrrhotite are seen in them. At times the elongated and bending nature of the pyrite crystals due to stress, are observed.

Galena: Galena is noticed very rarely and it is isotropic, and shows the characteristic triangular pits (Fig. 3). At places it is presenting with the gold, which is an interesting phenomenon observed by Safonov et al (1980) also.

Magnetite: It is anhedral showing weak anisotropism. A phenomenon namely martitization of the magnetite is observed. It mainly occurs as inclusions in hematite and arsenopyrite (Fig. 9).

Hematite: The mineral is present without any regular shape or form. It is anhedral and isotropic. It consists of magnetite inclusions (Fig. 11). In some cases the hematite and specularite association is observed. Hence the needles of specularite, confirm its presence due to the alteration of the hematite (Fig. 11).

Limitations and Conclusions:

Paragenetic sequence : The following are the general accepted and observed statements of the earlier workers.

Harder minerals like arsenopyrite, pyrite, magnetite and specularite, etc., in ores appear to have crystallized earlier than softer ones. The harder minerals are the most likely to be idiomorphic. Arsenopyrite, pyrite etc., commonly shown an approximately crystal outlines in polished sections. Where ever a hard mineral comes into contact with a soft one, it is decided that the harder one is the older. Crystals of a hard mineral such as pyrite and arsenopyrite, are filled with inclusions of softer ones such as pyrrhotite and in some cases, these are connected with more pyrrhotite that is outside, then they are said to be younger than pyrite are arsenopyrite.

Whatever may be the criteria to consider the age relationships is still inadequate leading controversies (Gilbert, 1924). That's why and also due to certain difficulties and limitations it is not possible to draw the paragenetic sequence in detail. However, the paragenetic sequence observed in the area is almost the same as noticed in the gold deposits of different regions.

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Figure. 1 : Euhedral pyrite grains
Parallel Nicols, 56X.

Figure. 2 : Arsenopyrite showing the poikilitic
nature in pyrrhotite Parallel Nicols, 56X.

Figure. 3: Galena and Magnetite showing
the poikilitic nature in pyrrhotite

Figure. 4 : Elongate and bending nature of
pyrrhotite grains Parallel Nicols 35X.

Figure. 5 : Broken – but undisturbed arsenopyrite
Grains Parallel Nicols 35X.

Figure. 6 : Big and deformed arsenopyrite
Grains Parallel Nicols 35X.

Figure. 7 : Cluster of deformed arsenopyrite grains Parallel Nicols 100X

Figure. 8 : Pyrrhotite and magnetite grains Parallel Nicols 35X.

Figure. 9 : Magnetite inclusions in arsenopyrite grains Parallel Nicols 56X

Figure. 10 : Vesicular basalt grains Parallel Nicols 35X.

Figure. 11 : Magnetite inclusions in hematite grains Parallel Nicols 56X.

Figure. 12 : Alteration of hematite into specularite grains

Figure. 13

Figure. 14

Figure. 15

Figures.13.,14., and 15. Filling process of mineralisation, specks of gold in arsenopyrite
Parallel Nicols 100X.

Figure. 16 : Vesicular basalt with mineralization in vesicles
Parallel Nicols 56X

Figure. 17

Figure. 18

Figures.17 and 18: Specks of Gold

Parallel Nicols 56X.